

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 22.02.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 30.04.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (118), 701-715

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.15314077

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ROR Id: <https://ror.org/04pm4x478>

Music for a Composer: Social Isolation of the New Music Scene in Turkey

Besteci için Müzik: Türkiye Yeni Müzik Sahnesinin Sosyal İzolasyonu

ABSTRACT

This article examines the social isolation of new music in Turkey by analyzing its institutional infrastructure, production mechanisms, audience engagement, and internal dynamics. Based on ethnographic fieldwork and interviews with composers, the study highlights the underdevelopment of key scene-making institutions—such as ensembles, venues, archives, media platforms, and funding bodies—and how this limits the dissemination and reception of new music. It shows how the scene is primarily rooted in academia, producing a composer-centric ecology in which composers take on multiple roles across creation, organization, and promotion. Operating in a highly individualized environment with limited local support, many composers turn to international collaborations, further distancing the local scene from global practices. The article calls for a reconfiguration of funding to empower a wider range of music professionals, the institutionalization of open commissions, and the fostering of collaborative structures among performers, scholars, media, and audiences, each holding distinct, recognized roles.

Keywords: new music, contemporary music, modern music.

ÖZET

Bu makale, Türkiye'deki 'yeni müzik' sahnesinin kurumsal altyapısını, üretim biçimlerini, dinleyiciyle etkileşimini ve iç dinamiklerini inceler. Etnografik saha çalışması ve bestecilerle yapılan görüşmelere dayanan araştırma, icracılar, konser mekânları, arşivler, medya ve kültürel finansman gibi temel bileşenlerin yetersizliğinin yeni müziğin alımlanışını sınırladığını ortaya koyar. Sahne, büyük ölçüde akademik kurumlar içinde var olmakta; bu da bestecilerin yaratım, performans, organizasyon ve tanıtım gibi birçok rolü üstlendiği besteci merkezli bir ekosisteme yol açmaktadır. Ancak icracılar, eleştirmenler, dinleyiciler gibi sahneyi canlı tutan aktörlerin eksikliği dikkat çekmektedir. Bu durum hem besteciler arası yaratıcı etkileşimi zayıflatmakta hem de onları uluslararası iş birliklerine yönlendirerek yerel ve küresel pratikler arasındaki mesafeyi artırmaktadır. Makale, daha kapsayıcı sahne yapıları için finansman modellerinin yeniden düzenlenmesini, açık çağrı sistemlerinin yaygınlaşmasını ve farklı aktörler arasında iş birliğini teşvik eden kurumsal yapılar geliştirilmesini önermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: yeni müzik, çağdaş müzik, modern müzik.

1. INTRODUCTION

Think of all the activities that must be carried out for any work of art to appear as it finally does. That is, the imperatives all operate if the event is to occur in a specific way and no other. But the work need not occur in that way, or in any other particular way. If one or another of these activities does not get done, the work will occur in some other way. If no one appreciates the work, it will go unappreciated. If no one supports its doing, it will go unsupported. If specific items of equipment are not available, the work will be done without them. Naturally, doing without any of these things affects the work produced. It will not be the same work. But that is far different from saying that it cannot exist at all unless these activities are performed (Becker, 1982/2008, p.5)

'*Yeni müzik*,' which translates to 'new music' in Turkish, represents a niche within the contemporary composition scene situated at the periphery of Turkey's intricate musical landscape. As a musical genre, new music resists confinement to specific definitions in terms of materials, techniques and styles¹; instead, it functions as a broad discourse and collection of practices across various musical and interdisciplinary domains, integrated within a network of art, education, and cultural institutions. Hence, as recently identified by Farnsworth and Grüny, it can be more accurately considered a discipline of contemporary music (2024, p.3), akin to Becker's art worlds. Reflecting the global individualization of styles, new music in Turkey similarly encompasses both modernist and postmodernist approaches from 20th-century (Western) art music practices, blending individual combinations and unique hybrid styles. Rather than being prominently featured in artistic manifestos or composer collectives, new music in Turkey is primarily visible through a select few local festivals such as *Bilkent Yeni Müzik Günleri* or *Bilgi Yeni Müzik Festivali*, thereby shaping a small, obscure musical scene centered on academia in Turkey.

As we have documented in an earlier study (Turan & Oğul, 2023) the localization process of new music in Turkey, is indirectly rooted in the Western Art Music tradition and has a negational relation to the national school of composition known as Turkish Contemporary Music, which was institutionalized during the early republican period's cultural policies and music reforms between the 1920s and the 1950s (see and (1984) and Tekelioğlu (2001) for detailed documentation of the music reforms). Although there were pioneering compositions by the mid-1950s *Helikon* circle as the earliest examples of modernist new music from Turkey, '*yeni müzik*' as a local critical discourse on cutting-edge contemporary music emerged in the 1990s, notably marked by the *1. Ankara Yeni Müzik Festivali* in 1989, organized by composer Ahmet Yürür (Turan & Oğul, 2023, pp.58-59; Ali, 1989, p. 5). It later gained institutional momentum among musicians in Istanbul's newly established music departments², and private art ventures in the late 1990s and early 2000s. Since the late 2000s, '*yeni müzik*' has evolved into an umbrella term encompassing a wide array of contemporary composition and performance practices in several music departments in major cities such as Ankara, İzmir, Eskişehir, alongside Istanbul.

This new formation of contemporary music diverges aesthetically from the earlier compositional framework, characterized by pre-modernist tendencies and their alignment with the nationalist policy of synthesizing Anatolian folk music idioms with polyphonic techniques and forms—a central approach still prevalent in many state institutions today³. The local new music scene is also distinct sociologically, setting

¹ Despite its widespread practical use in music ventures, the term 'new music' does not have a standardized definition as a category denoting specific musical qualities. There is ongoing debate about whether 'new music' should be reserved exclusively for critical and innovative approaches or if it should also include postmodernism, neo-styles, and crossovers with popular and alternative genres (Pamies, 2016). As documented by Heile (2009), the term historically originates from the German *Neue Musik* tradition, which is characterized by radical modernism and a critical stance on musical material and ideology. This tradition was first theorized by Paul Bekker (1923) and later by Adorno (2006) in 1949. However, scholars have pointed to the last quarter of the 20th century as the point of crystallization for styles and practices (Clarke, 2018, p.415), leading to a 'micro-specificity of substyles' (Lochhead, 2018, pp.419-420) and individualism. This period coincided with a global shift toward the English term 'new music,' which signifies a more neutral discourse, consolidating with postmodern practices that developed in the post-war period (Pace, 2022, p.22). What followed in post-war conditions was the American vernacular avant-garde, marked by ear-based practices and conceptual approaches that altered the definition of a musical work (Piekut, 2018, pp.439-441). Hence, 'new music' in its 21st century condition can be better conceptualized as a post-genre musically, yet defined by its boundaries of specific networks and practices of particular art institutions.

² Three educational institutions established in Istanbul in the late 1990s were instrumental in initiating local new music activities and nurturing the scene through their graduates over the years. These key institutions are Yıldız Technical University, Faculty of Art and Design (1999), Istanbul Technical University, MIAM (Center for Advanced Studies in Music, 1999), and Istanbul Bilgi University Music Department (1997/2005). Many composers who began their careers during the early event in the 2000s later assumed administrative and academic roles in the 2010s, as the *yeni müzik* discourse gained continuity in other institutions, most notably at private university departments such as Bilkent University and Yaşar University. The most significant local new music festivals are often organized by these departments, and each year around 8 to 10 departments collaboratively organize *Sesin Yolculuğu: Genç Besteciler Festivali*, constituting the most comprehensive, socially intersectional gathering of new music practitioners.

³ The Turkish Contemporary Music with synthesis aesthetics is most represented by Turkish Five and following generations of conservatory-based composers. National identity retaining function of this repertoire is most prominent in two genres. The first includes orchestral suites and tone poems that incorporate folk dance music, rhythms, and local myths, such as Rey's *Türk Manzaraları* (1928), Alnar's *Türk Sıiti* (1928), Saygun's *Halay Op. 24* (1942-44), and Erkin's *Köçekçeler* (1943). The second genre consists of polyphonic *türkü* (folk song) collections, such as Rey's *12*

itself apart from the former state-sponsored contemporary music sphere by representing a comparatively more civic and socially diverse community of musicians and institutions, in contrast to the bureaucratic mode of music-making in governmental institutions (Turan & Oğul, 2023, p. 61). The study posits that it embodies the innovative, experimental, and progressive sub-branch within the local contemporary music sphere, characterized by its emphasis on research-oriented practices, technological rigor, internationality, civic engagement and individuality, the democratization of compositional institutions and student orientation, thereby creating alternative avenues that challenge the ideology and aesthetics the preceding school.

Despite the dynamism in its initial establishment, the current scene of new music faces challenges related to its development and social relevancy. Drawing from Bourdieu's theory on taste and cultural capital (1984), one can discern the insular nature of contemporary arts within elite institutions as a prevalent sociological trend. Unsurprisingly, new music in Turkey also aligns with these academic, elite, and high art sectors, thus somewhat isolating it from broader society. Nonetheless, specific conditions unique to the local new music scene contribute to a notable degree of socio-economic isolation. One composer described this phenomenon as the 'ghost' status of local new music, while another likened it to fostering a 'pirate culture', where ideas and materials circulate within an environment that has yet to flourish with diverse professional agencies and be valued, preventing it from becoming a relevant cultural force and offering an alternative to its perpetual peripheral position in both global and local contexts.

The social isolation of new music practices and the underdevelopment of scene mechanisms, which is the focus of this article, are preliminary factors contributing to the marginalization of local new music practices. However, it is important to note that the overall socio-cultural isolation results from a complex set of issues, all of which are equally significant. These include unresolved cultural identity issues, the influence of modernist ideology and its antagonisms, the saturation of certain aesthetics, and a lack of viable local artistic discourses. This article, however, only discusses the underdevelopment of the scene and its social effects, providing insights into the material conditions of local new music and setting the stage for further exploration of other contributing factors in subsequent research. By doing so, it aims to navigate how new music becomes an elusive practice not only for the broader society but also for its practitioners.

This article is based on participant observation in events and interviews with new music composers that I conducted during my fieldwork⁴ from 2018 to 2022 for a larger study on the recent history and socio-cultural practice of the local scene (Turan, 2024). Methodologically, the study aligns with the growing literature on the ethnomusicology of Western art music (Born, 1995; Cook, 2008; Nooshin, 2011; Nooshin, 2014; Bayley et al., 2016; Usner, 2010), which incorporates ethnographic fieldwork practices and socio-cultural perspectives alongside the music analytical and historical approaches of traditional musicology. Although it draws from sociological studies of new music, local and global, narratively, it reports from the field, giving voice⁵ to its members' experience rather than providing quantitative data on the socio-economics of the field.

This discussion is hoped to be crucial as it describes critical insights from the conditions new music is created, produced, disseminated and perceived in Turkey. The study documents that the underdevelopment of the scene is marked by insufficient financial support, a scarcity of performance spaces and performers, limited and short-lived festivals, and a lack of diverse agencies for dissemination and audience engagement, collectively creating an environment that stifles growth, limiting visibility, and hinders the

Anadolu Türküsü (1926), Akse's *Çokseslendirilmiş Türküler* (1936), and Saygun's *10 Halk Türküsü Op. 41* (1968). The national mark of the 'synthesis aesthetic' remains prevalent as a norm in composition education at conservatories, state performance institutions, and state-organized composition competitions (Turan & Oğul, 2023, p.56-57).

⁴ As the initial phase of fieldwork, an open-ended qualitative survey was conducted at Arter's *Yeni ve En Yeni Müzik Festivali* (February 2020) to explore the meanings and local agencies of new music. Avoiding fixed definitions, the survey drew from the concepts of art worlds (Becker, 2008) and actor-network theory (Latour, 2005) to map key musicians, institutions, and conceptualizations of the scene. The responses provided an initial network of collaborators and field sites for participant observation, shaping the themes of subsequent interviews. Building on this, the main fieldwork involved 21 in-depth interviews with musicians—primarily well-established composers—conducted using Holstein and Gubrium's (1995) active interview method, participation in 22 seminars and workshops, observations at over 25 concerts, longitudinal studies of multiple editions of four major annually organized festivals, documentation of three album recording projects, and semester-long participation in a new music course. For detailed documentation, see Appendices B and C in Turan's study (2024, pp. 348–361).

⁵ The paraphrased statements used in this article are drawn from interviews conducted as part of my doctoral research. While the composers involved gave permission for their full quotations and identification to be used in my dissertation, in this article I have opted to anonymize their identities and only use paraphrased key notions that capture the general sentiments expressed. These paraphrased statements reflect the composers' commonly shared perspectives on the socio-economic conditions and challenges faced by the local new music scene in Turkey, as articulated in my original translations from Turkish. For detailed, full quotations and identified content from the interviewed composers, please refer to the dissertation (Turan, 2024).

appreciation and critique. Hence addressing these issues is essential for fostering a more vibrant and sustainable local new music scene. From a broader look, it invites the reader to look at the new music discipline from a peripheral perspective where its social issues might have been more clearly observable when capacities are insufficient in a culturally peripheral context.

2. CONDITIONS OF NEW MUSIC IN TURKEY

In Turkey, financial backing for new music endeavors primarily flows from universities, often in collaboration with cultural institutes and a select few private art foundations. This framework bears a notable resemblance to the Cold War-era university patronage of new music as research, characterized by a technocratic model advocated by figures like Milton Babbitt and facilitated by partnerships between universities and funding sources (Robin, 2018). However, a significant disparity lies in the constrained level of financial collaboration between academia and private and/or state funds within Turkey. In contrast to the American model, private funds and support for academic artistic activity are limited to providing concert spaces for project-based duration rather than direct and sustainable investment. In contrast to European models, where new music enjoys substantial governmental funding alongside private ventures, Turkey's new music scene largely operates also independently from state sponsorship. Although a few municipalities occasionally support new music events, and there are a few occasional state commissions, the new music landscape remains largely outside the activities of state-sponsored institutions, namely conservatories, symphony orchestras, and opera houses⁶.

Although emerging as potential patrons, private art ventures, on the other hand, also do not provide the required support and sometimes present new challenges to the sustainability of new music initiatives in their own ways. Private art spaces such as *Arter*, *Gedik*, *Salt* and *Borusan*, funding coming from big financial groups such as *Eczacıbaşı*'s commissions, or the occasional events of art associations of big companies like *İş-Sanat*, *AkSanat*, or *YapıKredi Kültür Sanat* have recently begun supporting new music activities. Some composers indicate that private art institutions promote new music better than university patronage and the state due to their better situatedness in urban daily life and marketing capacities. However, the presence of such ventures remains limited and in a developmental stage in the local scene, with only a few, such as *Borusan Sanat Evi*, demonstrating relatively consistent institutional involvement through regular activities beyond individual efforts. Moreover, these ventures typically prioritize popular high art products that are part of the alternative culture industry, such as jazz festivals or interdisciplinary multi-media projects, occasionally incorporating elements of new music, also as a niche, lacking familiarity with its conventions and unique history with autonomous music and expert authority. Hence, despite their emergence, creating at least an alternative platform, these newly developing art ventures do not fully meet the needs of local musicians.

This results in meager budgetary provisions for new music initiatives beyond the resources allocated by music departments themselves. This sometimes compromises the quality of new music activities, necessitating extensive voluntary efforts from organizers and posing various challenges for production and visibility that relate to the overall isolation of new music in Turkey to an extreme degree that the local scene of new music becomes hypothetical as one composer puts.

It is essential to acknowledge that being a composer of new music in Turkey does not constitute a profession conducive to sustaining a livelihood, as opportunities for composition commissions are exceedingly scarce. Moreover, it is commonplace, rather than exceptional, for the meager number of available commissions to remain unpaid as a normative practice. For example, none of the composers interviewed received financial support from government funds or remuneration for state commissions as of 2021 when we conducted the interviews. Similarly, none of the composers in projects sponsored by privately funded art institutions during my fieldwork have received payment for their commissions either. Notably, performers often receive fees for their contributions, whereas composers do not, with the mere performance and recording of their music being perceived as a form of compensation.

⁶ This separation stems from the localization of new music discourse in Turkey, which emerged as an alternative to the earlier state-sponsored nationalist school of composition known as Turkish Contemporary Music. After the state implementation of music reforms and establishment of Western-style music institutions between the 1920s-1950, the gradual decline of state cultural policies marginalized contemporary music, viewing it as an 'imported culture' or 'cultural hegemony' imposed by the early republic (Citations). The localization of new music discourse in Turkey emerged in the 1990s as an alternative to this earlier establishment, further complicating the situation. Consequently, new music, with its radically anti-nationalist discourse and unfamiliar aesthetics, has rarely been part of state-funded art activities. Despite the mentioned exceptions, the local new music repertoire is significantly underrepresented in state-funded commissions and programs.

While many composers privately acknowledge this issue during interviews, it is uncommon for them to raise it publicly, leading to its normalization within the scene and perpetuating the systemic neglect of the value of composers' expert skills. As Smith and Taylor observe for the British new music scene, when the opportunities for composition are not paid, this also affects the status of the composer's identity as an amateur rather than a professional (2019, p.600). One composer aptly reflects on the issue that new music started to be a luxurious hobby. Some composers indicated that this is not only a financial but also an existential problem; when a proper art world mechanism is lacking, the academic composer model becomes a necessity. Composers reflect that while anyone can become a new music composer, it is easier for the wealthy to compensate for the time and money needed to even catch the opportunities for success, which is not guaranteed and, in fact, is becoming increasingly competitive. This creates the category of emerging composers, as Smith & Thwaites refer, who are in their late 20s and 30s, well-trained, highly educated and experienced competent professionals without no financial stability (2019, pp.591-592). So similarly, despite the elite social connotations of the profession of composition, the strikingly contrasting low-level income and financial instability of new music make composers precarious workers rather than elites (Smith & Thwaites, 2019, p. 593).

These economic limitations make academic patronage a necessity that compensates for the insufficiencies, providing not only financial but also social capacities functioning as an art world by itself. University-based composers feel relative economic stability, performance opportunities for their works, and institutionally recognized professional prestige. As the new music activities occur in an academic setting, empowering composers as expert authorities with PhD positions and particularly promoting modernist artistic stands with research-based orientations (Robin, 2018, pp. 752-756), the confinement of local new music activity in academia also results in limitations in dissemination processes and engagement with the audience. It, for instance, often displays a unique concert setting similar to conferences, where we cannot observe normative (un-professional) audiences as a particular agency who witness and respond to music. Since it is considered part of an elite culture of academia from the onset of creation, it also affects the new music composers' poetics, musical materials and ideas and their social stand, creating a condition in which new music easily becomes a research presentation. While some composers find the setting suitable for new music, most recognize its difference as a musicking setting both from mainstream concert situations as well as from Western art music concert conventions that are already considered formal and inactive in terms of audience engagement.

Many composers critically reflect on the necessity of academic support for their work, but they also express concerns about how this relationship affects the engagement of new music with wider audiences and institutions. This tension raises questions about the artistic integrity of composers, both personally and within the community. One composer highlights that while academic institutions can be instrumental in helping composers achieve their artistic goals, the quality of music produced within academia is not always exemplary. They argue that while discussing the limitations of the academic environment is important, it often triggers resistance, as it challenges the very framework that supports their existence. The composer further emphasizes that in academia, where composition often remains a secondary pursuit, this dynamic can lead to a sense of inauthenticity. Another composer echoes a common critique, suggesting that the title of 'composer' should not automatically be granted to those who teach composition in academic settings, especially when they are not actively engaged in the compositional process. This critique points to a broader issue of legitimacy within academic structures, where individuals may receive recognition as composers without actively contributing to the field through their work.

Although some composers critically reflect on the role of academia in shaping the new music scene, noting that although academic patronage is necessary, it often raises doubts about how new music engages with both people and institutions. The lack of diverse stakeholders in the scene significantly hampers its visibility, growth, and long-term sustainability. Central to this issue is the absence of specialized platforms for critiques, reviews, and scholarly publications, which limits the broader dissemination of new music activities. Without dedicated magazines, websites, or discussion forums, there is little opportunity for critical engagement or for the genre to gain recognition in both academic and non-academic circles. This absence of resources, coupled with a lack of archiving and musicological work, weakens the historical record of the genre, undermining its credibility and place in the broader cultural landscape.

Moreover, the scene's reliance on university-based festivals and limited academic promotion restricts its outreach to the public. With minimal media presence, local new music examples struggle to engage audiences beyond specialized academic spaces. The disconnect between the genre and the general public leads to a lack of societal interest, compounded by limited coverage of concerts, premieres, and albums. As

a result, the field suffers from stagnation, with little constructive dialogue or recognition of new works. This lack of critical and appreciative culture further isolates the scene, preventing the development of a more vibrant and dynamic musical environment.

In addition to the absence of critical infrastructure, local new music endeavors often face substantial challenges in the professionalization of their output. The lack of agencies such as record labels, publishing houses, and professional curation teams often creates poor production capacities alongside exacerbating issues of visibility and dissemination. Without these crucial support structures, the quality of promotional materials such as liner notes and album production suffers in many steps of production. The reliance on volunteers (often composers) to handle multiple tasks, from logistics to sound engineering or marketing, leads to subpar presentations. This volunteer-driven approach inevitably undermines the quality and the standards of the profession.

Another issue mentioned by composers is that economic constraints significantly impact their international visibility, particularly the lack of state support. Without institutional backing, which is typically expected in many art fields, composers feel marginalized and isolated. The absence of recognition from established commissioning mechanisms, local publishing houses, record labels, ensembles, or associations leads to an overall sense of neglect. Practical challenges also arise, such as difficulties in traveling to foreign countries, as artists face obstacles due to a lack of formal support. Even highly established composers are forced to cover their own expenses and cannot rely on institutional support for their international engagements. Notably, none of the composers in this study received any governmental recognition for their successes abroad, despite their well-established professional status in Turkey. The absence of institutional foundations is seen as a significant disadvantage in the highly competitive world of new music, making it difficult for composers from Turkey to gain recognition as artists from the periphery. Some composers noted feeling rootless abroad, highlighting the challenge of gaining recognition when one is not even acknowledged in their own country. This lack of recognition makes their international reputation fragile, as their work is vulnerable to misinterpretation in the absence of the institutional context that typically provides a framework and legitimacy.

3. PERFORMANCE LIMITATIONS

The insufficiency of institutional funding necessitates extensive voluntary efforts from organizers and poses significant challenges for both production and visibility, contributing to the overall isolation of new music in Turkey. One of the most frequently voiced concerns is the limited number of opportunities for the performance of new music pieces. While this study does not take a quantitative approach, the scarcity of festivals and dedicated ensembles are self-evident.

The number of annually organized festivals in Turkey that are explicitly dedicated to the performance of new music compositions is currently four⁷, with three hosted and funded by private universities and one organized by a private arts foundation. State-funded art institutions or universities do not organize any festivals exclusively dedicated to new music or contemporary music. However, there are two⁸ annually held festivals, supported by state institutions that focus on contemporary music composition more broadly, where new music can find a place. All of these festivals are dedicated to the performances of composition students, and there are no regularly organized festivals that program mature works by well-established composers. Additionally, only one of them is organized through an open call, while the rest program the works of their own students or rely on closed selection processes, often based on the personal networks of the composers involved.

Among these, the longest-running new music festivals are *Sesin Yolculuğu – Genç Besteciler Festivali* and *Bilgi Yeni Müzik Festivali*. However, even these festivals, despite their relative continuity, face significant challenges—especially regarding performance opportunities—alongside broader financial inefficiencies. *Sesin Yolculuğu*, organized through the collaboration of composition departments from various universities in Turkey, does not have a permanent financial sponsor aside from temporary annual funds that cover basic expenses such as posters. The festival relies on universities and local municipalities to provide concert

⁷ The *Bilgi Yeni Müzik Festivali* has been organized by Istanbul Bilgi University since 2005. The *Bilkent Yeni Müzik Günleri* was established by Bilkent University in Ankara in 2011 and has continued under the name *Bilkent Composition Academy* since 2017, hosting regular concerts, seminars, and artist residencies. The *İzmir Yeni Müzik Günleri* has been organized annually by Yaşar University since 2019. *Yeni ve En Yeni Müzik Festivali*, organized by the private art venture *Arter* in Istanbul, has been held since 2020.

⁸ *Sesin Yolculuğu – Genç Besteciler Festivali* is organized collaboratively by various composition departments in Turkey since 2005, and *CANIS MAJORIS*, organized by Yıldız Technical University since 2017. This category could also include the *Maçka Elektrikli Müzik Günleri*, focused on electroacoustic contemporary music practices and organized by Istanbul Technical University since 2016; however, it is uncertain whether this festival has continued beyond 2022.

venues, while students from the respective institutions primarily perform student compositions. The entire process—from artistic production to performance, promotion, and organization—is conducted on a voluntary basis. Each year, chamber ensembles and chamber orchestras are formed specifically for the festival, but none of these ensembles have evolved into regularly performing professional entities. However, there are also improvements, such that since 2017, the festival has invited professional ensembles to perform a limited selection of student compositions. Across its 15 editions, only three local ensembles (*Hezarfen Ensemble*, *Diskant Ensemble*, and *Anadolu Nefesli Beşlisi*) and three international ensembles (*UMS n' JIP*, *Schallfeld Ensemble*, and *Ensemble Musikfabrik* as trio) have participated outside of student ensembles.

Another long-running new music event is the *Bilgi Yeni Müzik Festivali*, which has comparatively better resources as it is organized by a private university. For instance, it has more funding to hire professional ensembles and benefits from access to a professional recording studio for festival pieces. The festival also maintains collaborative ties with other private art ventures in Istanbul, such as *MIXER*, *Bronx Pi Sahne*, *kargART*, *SALT*, and *Arter*, which provide venues and assist with audience building through their broader contemporary art networks. However, the number of local ensembles that have performed at the festival remains limited to *Sa-Ne-Na* (a percussion ensemble specialized in post-minimalist music), *Hezarfen Ensemble*, and *Diskant Ensemble* across three editions, while the remaining editions hosted nine European-based ensembles⁹. Observable in the cases of the two festivals, a common critique within the scene is the limited number of regular ensembles in Turkey that can perform notated new music compositions in the traditional sense, making them the primary candidates for open calls at these festivals. Beyond these two, local performers are mainly involved in project-based collaborations rather than as part of well-established, regularly performing professional ensembles. Consequently, European ensembles are often invited to local new music festivals when funding permits. This situation underscores the lack of a more robust local infrastructure for contemporary music.

Several factors contribute to the scarcity of performance opportunities for new music. Many composers trace performance problems to the musicking notions of state conservatories, key institutions of instrumental training. Since new music pieces often require skilled performers trained in the European Art Music tradition but also familiar with extended techniques and complex notations, there is a dependency on conservatory graduate performers. However, performance education in Turkey is structured to train performers to play Common Practice Period music, having a pre-modernist repertoire in their curriculum. Hence, even the most successful local performers often have little experience or familiarity with new music canon and performing traditions. The later founded new music departments on the other hand, prioritized composition education, while performance training programs rarely took a central place. As a result, there are only a few performers that can collaborate with great number of new music composers.

The educational gap between composers and performers results in dissatisfaction on both sides. This phenomenon echoes George Edwards' (1990, pp.436-437) description of a mid-20th century European paradox, where performers, unfamiliar with new music repertoire, notations, and extended techniques, struggled to accurately perform increasingly detailed scores, leading to composer dissatisfaction. In a similar vein, local composers frequently express disappointment with the performance of their works, which fosters a reluctance to collaborate with local performers. Reflecting on his experience with a major symphonic orchestra in Istanbul, one composer described the disconnect between the expectations of new music as an extension of the Classical tradition and the reality of how it is performed, emphasizing the stark difference between the musical worlds they inhabit. Similarly, performers with whom I spoke after a final rehearsal of a newly composed orchestral piece expressed difficulty with the technical aspects of the piece, noting that they found it unnecessarily complex and challenging without clear meaning. Another composer, drawing from his experience organizing concerts in Ankara in the mid-2000s, noted that establishing a tradition or a performed repertoire of new music would be impossible without reforming the institutions responsible for training performers. He highlighted the primary challenge of finding competent and motivated performers. Many composers also point to resistance to new compositions among performers, particularly in state orchestras, alongside administrative neglect, which they attribute to conservatism and a lack of competence.

⁹ European ensembles that participated in *Bilgi Yeni Müzik Festivali* include the *Ensemble Garage*, *Ergon Ensemble*, *OERKNAL*, *Artefact*, *plug*, *Awkas Ensemble*, *Ensemble Plytopus*, and *Duo Gross & Schoute*.

The performance limitations in the local new music scene are often compensated by two regular non-governmental collectives, namely *Hezarfen Ensemble* and *Diskant Ensemble*, which are valued for their commitment to performing local new music repertoire and premiering significant 20th-century works in Turkey over the past decade. However, without state support or official ties to academic institutions, these independent ensembles remain fragile and unsustainable, particularly during economic crises or major disruptions like the 2020 pandemic. As evident in the interview with a member, *Diskant Ensemble* has faced numerous challenges since its formation, including hardship in finding suitable venues, financial compensation for performers, and the budget for new commissions, as well as limitations in dissemination and promotional activities. These difficulties, compounded by voluntary labor, lead to an environment where advocacy for new music performance is insufficient. He reflected on the struggle for survival in Istanbul, noting that performers interested in new music often face financial difficulties, making it difficult to justify the commitment to performing new works over pursuing more lucrative opportunities. This creates a scene where professional activities are almost entirely dependent on voluntary efforts. Another composer, based on his experience initiating a civic ensemble, explained that voluntary efforts are not sustainable beyond financial inadequacies, as maintaining organizational discipline becomes more challenging in such cases. He added that this also creates social problems when taking artistic initiatives, as certain individuals are forced to take on more active roles, leading to unregulated hierarchies.

Although composers recognize and collaborate with local performers, when possible, their experiences are often described as unsatisfactory. One composer reflected that while they understand the difficulty of making a living from new music performances and do not judge performers for this, their own experience with local performers has been disappointing in several ways, even when compensation is provided. The composer noted that performers often lack sufficient time for preparation, treating unprepared rehearsals as normal, and there is often little to no communication with the composer regarding expressive aspects of the music. Other composers have pointed out that the limited number of regular contemporary music ensembles in Turkey results in a lack of stylistic specialization in new music performances. One composer observed that new music, with its various aesthetic branches, requires performers who understand these stylistic nuances. However, in Turkey, pieces in significantly different styles, such as minimalism and new complexity, are performed by the same ensembles within the same programs. Many composers view this as indicative of the underdevelopment of the local scene, where these few ensembles and a small group of individual performers represent the only available options for performing any style of new music.

University-based new music festivals often invite European ensembles to address the limitations of local performers, creating a reliance on foreign visiting groups instead of promoting local performance-oriented projects. While many composers view the performance opportunities offered by university festivals as essential for their careers, financial constraints limit these collaborations to a few well-funded private universities, making them an incomplete solution. Furthermore, collaborations between composers and international visiting ensembles do not always contribute to a sustainable artistic environment. University festivals are predominantly focused on student pieces, which demand more collaboration than is often feasible. However, visiting ensembles typically receive scores only a few months before the event and often have no communication with composers until the first rehearsal in Turkey. Due to time constraints, these ensembles usually have only one or two rehearsals before the premiere. As one visiting performer noted, ideal new music collaborations would involve multiple meetings with composers, but these projects are often rushed, focusing on premieres and one-time encounters rather than long-term artistic partnerships. Additional challenges, such as language barriers, further complicate these already hurried collaborations.

Many of these university-funded festivals primarily aim to provide opportunities for students, often focusing on pieces by young composers whose works have not been performed before, rather than established ones. Organizers also prioritize offering opportunities to as many composers as possible, valuing quantity, diversity, and inclusion over quality. While this student-centered approach is essential, it inadvertently leads to an accumulation of student compositions, leaving little room for mature works of local new music, which rarely—if ever—get performed in local festivals. One composer noted that the energy of these festivals is often exhausted by showcasing young composers' music, with no lasting impact, which explains why new music is something no one remembers. This focus on early-career composers, combined with the lack of repeat performances of mature works, prevents the development of a lasting and well-established repertoire of Turkish new music.

However, despite these inconveniences, working with visiting international ensembles presents a crucial opportunity for local composers. Many local composers view these collaborations as a significant chance to achieve high-quality recorded performances of their pieces, enhancing their portfolios. Additionally, the

presence of visiting international ensembles allows local composers to focus purely on their compositional work without the need to manage every aspect of performance and dissemination—a luxury rarely afforded in the local context. Partnering with such high-quality performers elevates the dissemination of their work professionally and dedicatedly, thereby enhancing its reception.

Many composers argue that addressing these performance limitations requires promoting more local ensembles dedicated to regular performances. This approach could foster increased collaborations, commissions, and greater visibility for new music within the local community. Beyond these practical needs, some composers stress the particular importance of performance opportunities in sustaining an organic socio-cultural experience of new music within a peripheral scene. Reflecting on the impact of performance constraints, one composer observes that successful composition students and early-career composers lacking performance opportunities often choose to leave Turkey, while those who stay may abandon composition altogether after graduation unless they find supportive academic paths.

4. AUDIENCE, PUBLIC AND APPRECIATION

While academic patronage provides a sheltered space for some of the needs of new music production, it also raises questions about artistic modes of being. The problem deepens with the common observation regarding a fairly limited number of audiences and promoters for local new music activities. It was often the case, more than the exception that the audience of the field events consisted of professional musicians, students, academics from other fields, and the close circles of the musicians performing at the event and artists and art spectators from other contemporary arts.

Among other factors, the role of the academy as an artistic environment in shaping new music's relationship with the normative audience is worth discussing. Composers have varying perspectives on this issue. Some agree that the academic sphere contributes to the social isolation of new music, but they argue that the independence it offers from the mainstream culture industry makes the trade-off worthwhile. Composers acknowledge that while the academy provides a certain degree of freedom to create from a relatively independent and individualistic artistic stance, the downside is that composers risk becoming trapped within an excessively individualistic realm that no longer resonates with anyone, recognizing the challenge of cultural irrelevance. A significant number of composers accept the risk of social irrelevance as inevitable, viewing it as an inherent aspect of the genre and its historical trajectory. They compare composing new music to academic research, which, like new music, tends to be confined to universities and specialized circles.

In contrast to academic settings, concert situations that align more with contemporary urban art scenes tend to attract a more diverse socio-cultural demographic, contributing to the emergence of a relatively new and small middle-to-high-class socio-economic audience for contemporary art. This demographic has been developing since the late 1980s, alongside the shift towards a market-driven economy. Among the new music events, two of the most well-attended and engaging organizations I encountered were held in privately run art spaces that regularly host audiences of fine arts and performing arts rather than venues dedicated solely to music. Particularly evident in my post-concert interviews with both the audience and musicians at events hosted by *SALT* and *ARTER*, the venue itself significantly influences audience participation and the overall mood of the performance. These venues' integration with other contemporary art communities creates a more inviting atmosphere for listeners who may not otherwise engage with new music in more traditional settings. Furthermore, these organizations often prefer styles of new music that align with free improvisation, performance-oriented pieces, sound installations and multimedia works, rather than strictly notated acoustic ensemble music.

While composers seem to have accepted the limited appreciation and reception of new music, many remain open to engaging wider audiences without compromising their creative practices. This reflects a nuanced negotiation between autonomy and accessibility, which also influences musical aesthetics. The traditional Adornoian stance on the independence of new music from the cultural industry, with its emphasis on meaning-making through its own structure and materials, remains relevant. Marginal composers often adopt a more critical tone toward accessible new music, which is more open to socially constructed meanings. Music perceived as accessible to outsiders is frequently scrutinized for its 'seriousness' and the 'intentions' of its composer. Although this norm is not necessarily discursive, it still creates aesthetic hierarchies among new music styles. As a result, minimalist aesthetics, collective improvisatory practices, narrative/programmatic music, and electroacoustic performances are often relegated to the periphery and dismissed as the (incompetent) 'others' of new music.

This semi-hidden convention of musical hierarchies contributes to the social isolation of new music and its often-antagonistic relationship with audiences. Rooted in the critical tradition of *Neue Musik*, this Adornoian stance is seen by some as an exclusionary discourse that impedes the appreciation of new music. For certain composers, any external reaction—even hostility—is preferable to the absence of interaction and the vacuum of meaning and appreciation. However, the stereotype of new music composers as antagonistic or anti-heroic figures, seemingly at odds with their audiences and the social relevance of music, has solidified over time¹⁰. This antagonistic image, often considered ‘pretentious’ or ‘weird,’ is common not only among audiences and performers but also among composers, who occasionally parody it as a cliché of new music. Yet, others critically argue that such an authoritarian attitude lies at the heart of the genre’s social isolation and the derisive reactions it provokes.

While part of the elitist connotation arises from the rigidities of musical modernism, it is equally important to acknowledge that its antagonistic reception often stems from cultural unfamiliarity. This disconnect is shaped by significant disparities in cultural capital between local new music composers and mainstream audiences. Edwards (1990, p.437) explains that hostility toward contemporary music is less a reflection of its inferiority and more a consequence of its unfamiliarity—an inability to fully understand it. Drawing on the early 20th-century Spanish philosopher José Ortega y Gasset’s *The Dehumanization of Art* (1968), Edwards explores the social psychology of contemporary art reception, which bears many parallels to the experience of local new music. Gasset suggests that a spectator may feel a sense of ‘superiority’ when they comprehend a work of art, even if they dislike it. In contrast, when their dislike stems from an inability to grasp the work’s essence, they may experience humiliation. This humiliation, Gasset argues, often leads to a compensatory reaction, where the spectator expresses their indignation to restore a sense of control and self-assurance (as cited in Edwards, 1990, p.437).

In the local context, unfamiliarity with new music is deeply tied to the stark contrasts between the genre and Turkey’s prevailing cultural and artistic framework, especially under the last two decades of AKP rule. The art and culture policies implemented during this period have further marginalized Western music institutions, which were already in decline. Over the past twenty years, these policies have sparked popular controversies surrounding the perceived failure of Kemalist music reforms, while structural changes—such as proposed legislation to privatize state art institutions, key personnel appointments, and the reconstruction of symbolic buildings housing state music institutions—has led to years of displacement for orchestras. As a result, the limited public spaces where new music might have taken root have been rendered ineffective, existing in an artistic vacuum. The contemporary music scene, already lacking institutional and social power, has struggled to mount a consistent civil resistance against these trends, gradually becoming irrelevant in the broader societal narrative, along with the broader category of Western art music. On the aesthetical side, nationalist cultural policies, which favor a simplistic and figurative approach, leave little room for abstract art or music forms that contain hidden meanings, multiple interpretations, or complexities. The mainstream cultural understanding, largely shaped by the entertainment and tourism bureaucrats and sectors, tends to regard art practices as the exclusive domain of elites that needs to be popularized. Consequently, the cultural gap between the general public and enthusiasts of new music has grown, leaving almost no common ground. Moreover, the perceived obscurantism of new music figures exacerbates this cultural unfamiliarity, presenting a significant obstacle to its ecological localization in Turkey.

Although not fully representative of the authoritarian connotations often associated with modernist new music, one notable instance of engagement with the unfamiliar and the perceived elitism can be observed through *Islak Köpek*’s live-streamed TV performance, which reflects the broader public’s reception of new music in free improvisational style. On July 28, 2011, NTV aired a live performance featuring renowned film actress and director Serra Yılmaz alongside *Islak Köpek*, Turkey’s pioneer free improvisation

¹⁰ One of the key cases through which I had the opportunity to observe the social isolation and antagonistic image of the local new music scene was a qualitative survey I conducted with audience of *Yeni ve En Yeni Müzik Festivali* organized by Arter in 2020. The post-concert interviews revealed that the audience for this new music festival was not only limited in number, but also, based on the professional backgrounds stated by 21 out of 23 participants, composed primarily of professionals working in contemporary music, contemporary arts, academia, and the cultural industries, as well as music students. A particularly striking aspect of the survey was the diversity of responses to the question, “How would you define new music?” The most frequently selected definition was “musics that are new in terms of style, technique, discourse, presentation, or other features (never done / never heard before).” Notably, two other commonly selected definitions emphasized the oppositional nature of new music, which many participants considered central to its identity: “musics that compel their audience in terms of accessibility in comparison to normative music experiences, and demand knowledge, familiarity, effort, patience, and time from the listener,” and “musics that are new because of their opposition to the traditional/classical/tonal/old understanding of music.” A small number of respondents also preferred to offer their own descriptions rather than choose from the provided options, referring to the festival as “a festival of strange music,” “anti-capitalist music,” “anti-music,” “music made for weird people,” “serious music,” and “horror film music.” For a detailed documentation of the survey results, see Turan’s study (2024, pp. 348–356).

ensemble. This performance, characterized by a free-form improvisational approach, was a significant experiment aimed at expanding new music's exposure to a wider audience. Yılmaz collaborated with *Islak Köpek* on a project in which she recited the poem *Bezik Oynayan Kadınlar* by Edip Cansever, a figure associated with the modernist poetry movement called *İkinci Yeni*. Her recitation was accompanied by the ensemble's free improvisation (bmertg, 2011).

Following the live broadcast, social media platforms were flooded with comments from viewers who found the performance unusual. In response, a parody video titled *Entellikte Kulak Yakan Sınır* was created, offering a whimsical reimagining of Serra Yılmaz and *Islak Köpek's* performance. The original parody video, which was later lost, humorously mimicked the musicians' unconventional use of instruments and sounds, as well as the fragmented, gestural style of both the music and the recitation. Complete outsiders to music reenacted the performance using common household items, such as hairdryers and vacuum cleaners, in a humorous manner. After the release of the initial video, numerous versions emerged across YouTube and other platforms in the following years (Yallı, 2013; Alkışlarla Yaşıyorum, 2015; Ertürk, 2015).

Not only the performance itself but also the title of the first parody video resonated with a wide audience. The Turkish phrase *entellikte kulak yakan sınır* can be translated as the ear-piercing limit of intellectualism, which also carries the connotation of the intolerable boundary of intellectualism. In Turkish, *entel* (an informal, often pejorative term for intellectual) suggests a somewhat pretentious and snobbish identity. This phrase implies that *Islak Köpek's* performance surpassed the limits of auditory tolerance, even for those who adopt a façade of intellectualism, pretending to appreciate avant-garde or abstract art in order to be perceived as intellectually superior. This case offers a striking image of how new music is perceived within Turkish mainstream culture, with its connotations of intellectualism and its antagonistic relationship with the audience—even when this antagonism is not intentionally created. Moreover, it is a significant example as it is the only case in which avant-garde music has interacted with the mainstream and attracted public attention through mass media.

5. INDIVIDUALISM AND SOCIAL DETACHMENT AMONG COMPOSERS

Inspired by one of the conclusions in Bulut's (2007) thesis, I have engaged in conversations with composers about the social dynamics within their professional circles. Bulut's study primarily explores the use of rhythmic elements among the younger generation of Turkish composers. However, as part of his sampling method, he employed the snowball technique, where each composer refers to others and their works on the subject. Based on his observations of composers' referencing patterns, the author concluded that:

There is no meaningful communication network among young Turkish composers. As a result of this, composers do not show interest in each other's works and are not sufficiently familiar with the works of others. According to the composers' expressions, their similarities are limited to commonalities in their educational backgrounds. This lack of communication prevents them from being aware of their musical similarities and from creating a unified Turkish music school today (Bulut, 2007, p.114)

In line with Bulut's observation, I asked each composer to reflect on the social dynamics within the new music scene and to identify the composers and new works they regularly followed. Many responses referenced colleagues working within the same institutions, suggesting that social interactions among composers are primarily institution-based rather than driven by artistic or intellectual affinities. Another notable observation was the general dissatisfaction composers expressed regarding the aesthetic approaches of their peers, as well as their tendency to distance themselves from the local repertoire of new music, which they often perceived as lacking originality and technical competence. As a result, their assessments of the scene were predominantly negative, while they positioned themselves as detached individualists within it.

However, they also noted that the small scale of the composer community and the absence of well-developed scene mechanisms limits the potential for healthy competition and artistic exchange. Instead, the focus shifts toward consolidating a shared professional identity, defined more by defensive solidarity in response to collective challenges than by a genuine spirit of artistic collaboration. Rather than engaging critically with one another's work, composers tend to emphasize their collective professional struggles. This protectionist stance, however, does not extend to other key agencies within the music ecosystem, such as performers, audiences, or scholars. Instead, composers often adopt a critical attitude toward these groups, further reinforcing the social isolation of the new music scene through the prevalence of extreme individualism, antagonistic social attitudes and the composer-centric nature of its social structure.

The isolation of composers and their tendency toward extreme individualism can also be understood as part of the opportunity-driven culture that new music scenes often impose (Smith & Taylor, 2019, p. 600). Extreme individualism and a reserved social stance are frequently regarded as markers of artistic authenticity. However, they also function as strategies for navigating the socio-economic structural challenges of career development. As composers adapt to an environment characterized by scarce opportunities, the resulting climate of insecurity renders artistic discourse increasingly precarious. In this context, success serves as a gateway to the professional elite, conferring institutional legitimacy, whereas a lack of recognition is often attributed to personal inadequacy rather than systemic issues. Consequently, those who do not achieve recognition may find themselves marginalized, invalidated, and acutely aware of the perceived dispensability of their skills. In response, they may adopt a non-discursive stance to maintain access to opportunities and avoid jeopardizing future prospects. Conversely, successful composers may also become less engaged in artistic and intellectual discourse, as their integration into institutional structures fosters a vested interest in maintaining the status quo.

6. TRANSFORMING THE COMPOSER-CENTRIC PARADIGM OF NEW MUSIC

The overall sphere of the new music in Turkey scene has a variety of domains in which we can observe a socially isolated practice of musicking rather than a socially centered situation of musicking with a diverse range of engaged agencies collaborating on art appreciation. The underdevelopment of the scene can be seen as a holistic failure in the ecosystem necessary for the arts to thrive. Essential agents such as performers, promoters, critics, audiences, support personnel, economic funders, scholars, managers, and curators are either lacking or insufficient. This deficiency forces composers to assume all these roles, resulting in a composer-centric environment where composers are the sole drivers of the local new music activity.

Even if not all composers explicitly problematize this state of isolation, it remains a defining characteristic of how the local practice of new music exists, as Becker insightfully highlights in the opening quote. In this context, the most reliable generalization an observer of the scene can make about new music in its local context is that it is music for composers, as they are its central—and often sole—agents. However, as discussed in the previous section, it is even debatable whether it is truly for composers or merely for the individual composer, given that even the professional community itself exhibits a lack of interest in one another's artistic endeavors.

Social isolation gives rise to several documented challenges. When composers attempt to manage all aspects of the scene under constrained conditions, the resulting work often lacks the necessary quality to foster a thriving new music environment. Crucial components such as repertoire development, score archives, regular performance venues, scholarly studies, critical platforms, funding mechanisms, professional guilds, journals, and other media are either underdeveloped or handled in an amateur manner by composers themselves. The overemphasis on composers assuming multiple roles ultimately diminishes the overall quality of new music activities. By acting as organizers, educators, and administrators, composers are frequently required to operate outside their areas of expertise, leading to suboptimal outcomes.

Additionally, this composer-centric structure perpetuates issues of legitimacy and fosters a cycle of exclusivity, elitism, and pretense. As a result, the scene becomes increasingly insular, further alienating potential audiences and other stakeholders essential for cultivating a dynamic and sustainable music culture. The absence of a diverse and supportive infrastructure not only hinders the organic growth of new music but also reinforces its status as a niche field, struggling to achieve broader cultural relevance and impact. Without mechanisms that facilitate accessibility, engagement, and interdisciplinary exchange, it remains confined to a small, self-referential community, limiting its potential for artistic and institutional development.

In response to these challenges, composers frequently turn to the international networks they established during their studies abroad, actively seeking opportunities to collaborate through international competitions, commissions, and ensembles whenever feasible. Additionally, the opportunities afforded by digitalization and enhanced connectivity, which have significantly broadened access to musical materials and communities, have further accelerated the international integration of the local scene. Furthermore, within the socio-political framework of international art music organizations focused on promoting cultural diversity and the inclusion of underrepresented groups over the past decade, local musicians have increasingly been embraced within global music centers. For some composers, these developments have effectively alleviated the social and cultural constraints that previously hindered their engagement with the broader international music community.

Yet, while the integration with international scenes offers significant opportunities, it also poses challenges for the scene's position within the global-local framework. The heavy reliance on international networks and institutions for support—such as access to ensembles, commissions, and performances—has led to a pronounced international orientation. This reliance shapes both the aesthetics and the artistic discourses within the scene, positioning it at the periphery of the global new music centers. The limitations of the local scene compel composers to engage more deeply with international networks to access the resources necessary for their artistic development. However, as these international engagements intensify and as local musicians adopt the professional language, references, and value systems of the global music world, its connection to local contexts weakens when this cultural capital is not contextualized in the local practice. Consequently, the focus shifts away from local development, exacerbating the gap between local and global practices. Ironically, this growing disconnection perpetuates the scene's peripheral status, even as it seeks to localize. This gap not only stifles the emergence of a distinct local discourse but also undermines the recognition in both local and international contexts. As a result, *yeni müzik* as a local cultural phenomenon becomes a scene struggling to define its identity, unable to flourish in either its local or global context.

To address the social isolation and underdevelopment of the scene, several structural changes are necessary, with a focus on fostering a more collaborative, inclusive environment. First of all, a fundamental shift toward decentralizing the composer-centric structures of the scene is required for a more socially inclusive and viable local ecosystem. By actively involving a wider range of stakeholders—such as performers, curators, scholars, and arts administrators—the scene can move beyond the limitations of a composer-dominated model. These stakeholders bring essential expertise in areas like performance, archival work, critical discourse, and funding, all of which contribute to the long-term sustainability of new music practices. Recognizing the value of these diverse professional roles will create opportunities for establishing dedicated platforms for new music, such as score archives, performance venues, and platforms of critique. This shift would reduce the overburden on composers, enabling them to focus more on their creative processes and less on administrative tasks, thereby fostering a healthier and more sustainable artistic environment.

Increasing financial support through state funding, private sponsorships, and targeted grants is another critical component for fostering a sustainable scene. This support should be designed through collaborative efforts between local and international institutions, with a focus on long-term, sustainable investments rather than project-based funding. However, a critical aspect of fostering a sustainable scene lies in redesigning the financial funding mechanisms to prioritize performers alongside other key stakeholders such as curators, administrators, and scholars. Performers are the backbone of any music scene, and their active involvement is essential for bringing new compositions to life, ensuring that new music does not remain confined to theoretical or compositional spaces but is translated into dynamic public performances. Therefore, funding initiatives must be structured in a way that directly supports performers—especially those who specialize in contemporary music—by providing them with resources to commission new works or take part in selections, initiate collaborations as active agencies, and perform in diverse contexts including creative processes. Furthermore, this approach should be extended to other critical contributors to the ecosystem, such as critics, scholars, curators, promoters, and those involved in documentation, marketing, and visibility efforts. These stakeholders play an integral role in shaping the discourse surrounding new music, as well as ensuring that it reaches broader audiences and gains cultural relevance.

The final suggestion to address the social isolation of the local new music scene emphasizes the need for greater transparency and diversification in decision-making processes. Currently, the scene is dominated by closed, composer-centric networks, which stifle broader collaboration. To break this pattern, it is essential to establish open call practices for new music projects, a crucial step toward creating an inclusive and dynamic environment. These calls should involve not only composers but also performers, ensembles, and musicologists, ensuring that all stakeholders have a voice in the creative process. By diversifying the evaluation process through the inclusion of ensembles and scholars, it would be possible to ensure that a single group does not monopolize platforms for showcasing new music. Additionally, fostering a critical culture through music journalism and discussion platforms is vital. Dedicated spaces for reviews and critiques would encourage constructive feedback, normalize critical engagement, and promote higher artistic standards, while also providing accountability. Ultimately, such practices would not only make new music more visible and accessible to the public but would also elevate the standards of the scene, encouraging a more dynamic, transparent, and accountable local community of new music.

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